

Newly Diagnosed Genitourinary Malformation in a 73-Year-Old Male

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CLINICAL IMAGE

Photo of a patient with known cognitive deficit but with no previous medical appointments. On examination the patient was shown to have some genital alterations and his abdominal wall had a middle-line hernia, with no signs of suffering. His abdominal computed tomography scan showed a major infra umbilical middle line hernia with a lobular form, with no direct relationship with the inguinal channels. It was filled with small intestine but without signs of occlusion or incarceration. There was also evidence of subcutaneous tissue densification on the supra-pubic region, with abdominal wall ulceration towards the pre-vesical Retzius space. Due to social shaming and being part of a family with low resources he had never been studied for his pathology. Somehow he managed to survive up to 73 years of age with a congenital malformation of the genitourinary tract with an extrofic bladder, epispadism, abdominal wall deformity, and cognitive deficit.

